

Supply chains, especially those for smartphones, are complex.

Hundreds of companies worldwide are involved in the process, from raw material extraction and component manufacturing to the finished smartphone.

Human rights violations can occur at every stage, such as the financing of armed conflicts through profits from raw material extraction, exploitation, and a lack of safety standards for workers.

A completely “fair” smartphone does not currently exist, as it is virtually impossible to fully trace supply chains. Efforts and successes in establishing fair supply chains vary greatly depending on the brand [1-4].

35% of people in Germany have purchased a used smartphone or other IT device in the last two years, with the percentage rising to 55% among people between 16-29 years old [5].

The average lifespan of a smartphone in Germany is 2.5 years [6].

The collection rate for old electronic devices was only 31.7% in 2022, which is significantly below the legally required minimum rate of 65% [7].

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